

Excess adsorption of β -lactoglobulin on the soft surface of casein powder[†]

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Abstract : Extents (Γ_2^1) of adsorption of globular milk protein β -lactoglobulin (β lg) from salt solution onto the soft surface of casein powder have been measured as functions of β lg concentration at pH 6.5 keeping ionic strength and temperature constants. Ionic strengths were maintained by using neutral salts LiCl, NaCl, KCl, RbCl, CsCl, CaCl₂ and Na₂SO₄. Six molar concentration of denaturant urea was also used for the study of adsorption. Except KCl and KCNS, Γ_2^1 in the presence of other salts and urea respectively are positive. Values of Γ_2^1 in all cases increases with increase of C_2 for β lg concentration in the bulk phase. Γ_2^1 also increases with increase of C_2 until at a critical value C_2^m , it attains the maximum value Γ_2^m at the state of surface saturation. Values of Γ_2^m stands in the order :

This order is partly agreeing with lyotropic or Hoffmeister series effect. Γ_2^1 for KCl and KCNS are negative in sign at all values of C_2 due to the excess positive hydration of β lg in the presence of these salts. The maximum affinities of adsorption at the state of surface saturation represented by the free energy decrease $-\Delta G^0$ calculated from the use of integrated form of the Gibbs adsorption equation in kJ per kg of casein varies linearly with increase of Γ_2^m and average values of the free energy change $-\Delta G_B^0$ calculated from the slope of this plot is 38 kJ per mole of adsorbed β lg in all cases.

Keywords : Excess adsorption, beta-lactoglobulin, casein powder, lyotropic series, adsorption on soft surface, adsorption free energies.

Introduction

Proteins, nucleic acids and polysaccharides are main biopolymer constituents of living systems which may remain in soluble or insoluble states in contact with aqueous solvent. Adsorption of soluble proteins on various inorganic crystalline and rigid surfaces of particles from the aqueous solution has been extensively studied by many workers¹⁻¹⁰. However adsorption of proteins and nucleic acids on the surfaces of soft hydrophilic and insoluble substances under various conditions have been investigated only recently^{11,12}. Thus soluble proteins BSA, gelatin and DNA are shown to be adsorbed on the soft surfaces of insoluble biopolymers like casein at acidic pH, cellulose in the presence of various inorganic salts and urea. Role of hydration for such adsorption processes has been critically examined in terms of Hoff Meister or lyotropic series.

Milk behaves as naturally occurring colloidal system^{13,14} at and above pH 7.0. The stability of this colloidal system depends upon the interaction of milk protein casein, with β -lactoglobulin, milk fats and various inorganic salts present in the system under controlled physicochemical conditions. Thus major milk protein casein remains in micellar state^{12,15-17} at and above pH 7.0 whereas below this pH, casein in aqueous media remains in precipitated state in contact with milk whey in which milk protein β -lactoglobulin (β lg), remains soluble¹⁸.

An attempt will be made in this paper to study the adsorption interaction of soluble β lg on the hydrophilic surface of insoluble casein powder at pH 6.5 in the presence of various inorganic salts and urea respectively. The role of protein hydration and lyotropic series effects in the presence of these salts will also be examined in detail from the study of β lg adsorption on the soft surface of casein.

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

Materials :

β -lactoglobulin from Bovine Milk (Sigma No. L6879) was used as adsorbate. It was dried in a desiccator containing fused CaCl_2 for 2 weeks. Adsorbent was powdered fat-free casein of N. B. Chemicals, Cleveland, USA. It was also dried in a desiccator containing fused CaCl_2 for 2 weeks. Inorganic salts (NaCl , LiCl , KCl , CsCl , RbCl , CaCl_2 , Na_2SO_4 and KSCN) were all of analytical grades used. Folin reagent together with copper sulfate solution was used for the protein estimation. All these are of analytical grade and hence used directly without further purification. Urea was twice recrystallized from warm ethanol. Double distilled water was used throughout the adsorption experiments. Stock solutions of different inorganic salts of fixed ionic strength were prepared. These solutions were brought to same pH by addition of requisite volume of dilute HCl or NaOH solutions. Stock β -lactoglobulin (βlg) solution was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of protein in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The pH values of all the solutions thus prepared were measured with a digital pH meter (Testronix 511) with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH.

Adsorption experiment :

A fixed amount W (5×10^{-4} kg) of dry fat-free whole casein was taken in different standard joint stoppered round bottom conical flasks each of capacity 250 ml. In each flask, a fixed volume, V (equal to 40 ml) of βlg solution of molar concentration (C_2^i) was taken. The ionic strength of the solution was fixed by suitable addition of sodium chloride. The average pH of the aqueous solvent in each case was close to 6.5. The stoppered flasks containing adsorbate (βlg) and adsorbent (casein powder) were then shaken gently on a horizontal shaker for 24 h at constant temperature of 28 °C.

The temperature of the system was kept constant by using an air-thermostat (± 0.1 °C accuracy). The flasks were taken away from the shaker and kept undisturbed for another 24 h to allow adsorbent casein to settle down. At adsorption equilibrium, the supernatants by spectrophotometric examination were found to be free from any suspended particles after centrifugation at 5000 rpm. Estimation of βlg in the supernatant after adsorption was carried out by Lowry method¹⁹. The absorbance of blue color in this solution was measured with Hitachi U2000 spectrophotometer at 750 nm wavelength against the blank set. Ten sets of βlg solutions of known concentrations were prepared as standard. All of these solutions were treated with Folin reagent. To obtain the standard curve, the absorbance of these solutions measured at 750 nm

against that of a blank solution were plotted against known protein concentration. The unknown (molar) concentration of βlg protein (C_2) present in supernatant was evaluated using this standard curve. When needed, the unknown solutions of higher βlg concentrations were diluted with known volumes of solvent before measuring absorbance. The extent of adsorption Γ_2^1 in moles βlg per kg of dry casein at pH 6.5 and at a fixed temperature may be calculated using eq. (1),

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \frac{(C_2^i - C_2)V^t}{1000} \quad (1)$$

Here C_2^i and C_2 are molar concentrations of βlg before and after adsorption. Molecular weight of bovine β -lactoglobulin containing two subunits was taken as 36000, V^t is the volume of the β -lactoglobulin solution in ml associated per kg of dry casein. V^t is equal to V/W . Average error for the determination of C_2 never exceeded 3% so the error in the calculated value of Γ_2^1 remains in between 5–10%. W is the weight of dry casein in kg present in the system. The moisture content of casein powder and βlg have been determined by heating a known weight of the protein powder at 105 °C for 24 h followed by weighing. Average values of water contents for casein and βlg (dried in CaCl_2 desiccator) are found to be 1.0 and 1.5 percent respectively. All results of Γ_2^1 are expressed in terms of weights of dry proteins.

Excess adsorption :

The amount of adsorption of the soluble protein component (adsorbate) from aqueous solution to the surface region of casein has been calculated using eq. (1). We observe from this equation that when C_2^i is greater than C_2 , Γ_2^1 becomes positive and βlg will be accumulated in positive excess on the surface of casein. But in several cases, it has been noted that C_2^i is less than C_2 so that Γ_2^1 becomes negative due to the excess hydration of casein forming the soft surface. The molar concentrations of soluble protein (βlg) in these experiments are very low so that C_2^i and C_2 may be considered to be equal to molal concentrations m_2^i and m_2 before and after adsorption process¹⁹.

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \frac{W^t}{1000}(m_2^i - m_2) \quad (2)$$

For dilute solution, V^t may be replaced by W^t , the weight of the solvent in grams present in solution per kg of casein powder. It may alternatively be considered that before adsorption, n_2^i moles of solute (βlg) per kg of

casein powder is associated with n_1^t moles of solvent (per kg casein) so that

$$m_2^t = \frac{1000 n_2^t}{M_1 n_1^t}$$

After adsorption, the molality changes to m_2 where

$$m_2 = \frac{1000 n_2}{M_1 n_1}$$

Here n_2 moles of a free solute become associated with n_1 moles of free solvent per kg of casein powder at adsorption equilibrium. W^t is also equal to $n_1^t M_1$ when M_1 is the molecular weight of solvent water.

Inserting values of m_2^t , m_2 and W^t , eq. (2) may be written in the following form,

$$\Gamma_2^1 = n_2^t - n_1^t \frac{n_2}{n_1} \quad (3)$$

Γ_2^1 may be termed as moles of excess solute from solution adsorbed by one kg of adsorbent.

The excess of solvent component adsorbed per kg of adsorbent casein may be defined as¹¹,

$$\Gamma_1^2 = n_1^t - n_2^t \frac{n_1}{n_2} \quad (4)$$

Both eqs. (3) and (4) when combined we note

$$\Gamma_1^2 = -\Gamma_2^1 \cdot \frac{n_1}{n_2} \quad (5)$$

From definitions of concentrations and mole fractions for dilute binary solution, we find,

$$\frac{X_2}{X_1} = \frac{n_2}{n_1} = \frac{m_2}{55.5} = \frac{C_2}{55.5} \quad (6)$$

Here X_1 and X_2 stand for mole fractions of solvent and solute components respectively.

Combining relations (5) and (6)

$$\Gamma_1^2 = -\Gamma_2^1 \frac{X_1}{X_2} \quad (7)$$

or,

$$\Gamma_1^2 = -\Gamma_2^1 \frac{55.5}{m_2} \quad (8)$$

$$\approx -\Gamma_2^1 \frac{55.5}{C_2} \quad (8a)$$

The above three eqs. (7), (8), (8a) indicate that excesses of solute Γ_2^1 and solvent Γ_1^2 are not independent but are related to each other¹¹. If Γ_2^1 is known using eq. (1) Γ_1^2 can be calculated using values of m_2 or C_2 in relations (8) and (8a).

Further, if Γ_2^1 is positive, Γ_1^2 is negative and vice versa. Values of n_1^t and n_2^t each may be divided into parts^{19,20},

$$n_1^t = n_1 + \Delta n_1 \quad (9)$$

$$n_2^t = n_2 + \Delta n_2 \quad (10)$$

Here Δn_2 and Δn_1 moles of β lg and solvent components respectively are bound in absolute amounts to one kg of casein powder. Also n_2 and n_1 are moles of these components remaining free at adsorption equilibrium. Inserting these values of n_2^t and n_1^t from eqs. (9) and (10), to relations (3) and (4) respectively we shall find,

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \Delta n_2 - \Delta n_1 \cdot \frac{C_2}{55.5} \quad (11)$$

$$\Gamma_1^2 = \Delta n_1 - \Delta n_2 \cdot \frac{55.5}{C_2} \quad (12)$$

If the plot of Γ_2^1 against C_2 based on experimental data becomes linear, Δn_1 and Δn_2 values of solute and solvent respectively can be calculated from the intercept and slope of the plot¹⁹.

Results and discussion

The pH of milk for living mammalian system is usually close to 7.0. Casein precipitate near at pH 6.5 was chosen to perform the adsorption experiments. Casein present as major milk component is made up of many types of polypeptides. The main types are α S1-casein, α S2-casein, β -casein and κ -casein (2). There are trace amounts of γ -casein occurring in natural milk on account of limited proteolysis of β -casein by plasmin. However, all these proteins remain in the form of soluble micelles¹² whose structures have been widely studied using various techniques. By the addition of acid, enzyme rennin and few other additives, the casein micelles from natural milk associates and precipitates out¹². The precipitated protein in denatured form is found to bind large amount of water and milk fat and these are used for the preparations of various types of milk based foods. The surface of the casein powder appears to be soft and hydrophilic. From the study of water vapor adsorption by isopiestic method, powdered defatted casein is found to adsorb considerable

amount of water vapor both in the presence and absence of various types of inorganic salts^{12a}.

The milk protein β -lactoglobulin is a globular protein. It consists of two polypeptide subunits¹⁴ each of molecular weight 18000. The amino acid sequence of polypeptide chains have been determined for milk obtained from cow, buffalo, goat and human beings. The genetic varieties of all these animals and human beings have been established in terms of difference of position of amino acids within the polypeptide chains. Since β -lactoglobulin from milk belongs to globulin group, it was found to be insoluble in pure water but soluble in the presence of low concentration of an inorganic salt (salting in effect). Average β -lactoglobulin content of milk whey is 0.6 percent.

In Fig. 1, the adsorption isotherms of β lg on casein powder in the presence of 0.05 M and 0.01 M NaCl concentrations respectively have been presented at 28 °C and pH 6.5. Γ_2^1 is observed to increase sharply for NaCl concentration equal to 0.05 M at very low β lg concentration indicating strong interaction of β lg with soft surface

Fig. 1. Plot of Γ_2^1 against C_2 in the presence of neutral salts, pH 6.5 : (◆) NaCl, 0.05 M, 28 °C; (■) NaCl, 0.01 M, 28 °C; (○) Na_2SO_4 , 0.05 M, 28 °C; (Δ) NaCl, 0.01 M, 40 °C.

of casein. With the increase of C_2 , Γ_2^1 increases gradually until at a critical value C_2^m , Γ_2^1 reaches a maximum value Γ_2^m which remains constant with further increase of C_2 . For dilute solution, $C_2^m/55.5$ is equal to X_2^m , the critical concentration in mole fraction unit since $X_1=1$. From eq. (11) it indicates that the casein bound water at this state has been completely removed¹⁹ due to saturation of casein surface by β lg so that $\Gamma_2^m = \Delta n_2$. Values of X_2^m and Γ_2^m are included in Table 1. In Fig. 1 the

Table 1. Adsorption of β lg on casein in presence of various salts, pH 6.5, 28 °C

Sl. no.	Salts	Molar conc. (M)	$\Gamma_2^m \times 10^3$ (mol β lg/kg casein)	$X_2^m \times 10^3$	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ/kg casein)	$-\Delta G_B^0$ (kJ/mol β lg)
1.	NaCl	0.05	1.70	0.022	0.065	38.3
2.	NaCl	0.01	1.11	0.033	0.041	37.3
3.	Na_2SO_4	0.05	2.02	0.043	0.073	36.6
4.	LiCl	0.05	1.17	0.018	0.045	39.1
5.	CaCl_2	0.05	0.576	0.032	0.020	36.3
6.	CsCl	0.05	0.833	0.021	0.031	38.2
7.	RbCl	0.05	1.24	0.021	0.048	38.5
8.	Urea	6	2.71	0.066	0.090	33.4

isotherm for 0.01 M NaCl at 28 °C has been presented. The initial increase of Γ_2^1 with C_2 is practically zero. This indicates that β lg interaction with casein surface is negligibly small at low values of protein concentration. However as value of C_2 is increased, Γ_2^1 for higher values of β lg concentration begins to increase until at a critical value C_2^m (or X_2^m), Γ_2^1 reaches limiting value Γ_2^m . These are included in Table 1. One finds from this Table that for decrease of NaCl concentration from 0.05 M and 0.01 M, Γ_2^m is reduced considerably. When NaCl concentration is diluted from 0.05 to 0.01 M probably a β lg molecule attached to the surface needs more space on the soft surface. It is of interest to note that with increase of temperature 28 to 40 °C (Fig. 1), β lg is negatively adsorbed due to the excess solvent adsorption by casein, so that Γ_2^1 in the whole range of C_2 becomes negative. Further at 40 °C, Γ_2^1 - C_2 plot is linear in wide range of C_2 so that according to eq. (11) values of Δn_1 and Δn_2 are 2600 moles of solvent and 0.73×10^{-3} moles of β -lactoglobulin per kg of casein respectively.

In Fig. 1, the isotherm for β lg adsorption on casein powder has been presented in the presence of Na_2SO_4 of molar concentration 0.05 M. In the low range of β lg concentration, Γ_2^1 slowly increases with increase of C_2 but it increases to high value Γ_2^m when C_2^m (or X_2^m) is high (vide Table 1) in magnitude. At this state of maximum binding of β lg, value of Δn_1 for casein should be zero¹⁹.

In Fig. 2, the isotherms for adsorption of β lg onto the surface of casein at 28 °C and ionic strength 0.05 M have been presented for LiCl, CsCl, RbCl and CaCl_2 . In all these cases, Γ_2^1 is either zero or negative in the low range of C_2 but at C_2 close to 1.0×10^{-5} M, Γ_2^1 sharply increases to positive values for LiCl, RbCl and CsCl.

Fig. 2. Plot of Γ_2^1 against C_2 in the presence of neutral salts, pH 6.5, 28 °C : (\diamond) LiCl, 0.05 M; (\square) CaCl₂, 0.05 M; (\circ) RbCl, 0.05 M; (\times) CsCl, 0.05 M.

Such increase is observed for CaCl₂ at C_2 close to 1.5×10^{-5} M. At lower values of C_2 for LiCl, CsCl and CaCl₂, Γ_2^1 appears to reach maximum value Γ_2^m at appropriate critical values X_2^m (vide Table 1). For RbCl also, Γ_2^1 reaches sharply to the value Γ_2^m at their critical value X_2^m (vide Table 1) but in this case, Γ_2^1 sharply decreases from the value of Γ_2^m for $C_2 \gg C_2^m$ due to the excess rehydration of the β lg-casein complex. This excess rehydration is not observed for the β -casein complex in presence of NaCl, LiCl, CsCl and CaCl₂.

Negative adsorption and hydration :

In Fig. 3, the isotherms for adsorption of β lg on casein at 28 °C have been shown in the presence of 0.01 M KCl. One finds that all values of Γ_2^1 are negative since casein²¹ and β lg²² in the presence of concentrated KCl solution become extensively hydrated. For this reason m_2^1 in eq. (2) becomes greater than m_2 and Γ_2^1 becomes negative. In this respect, the behavior of the isotherm at 28 °C for KCl (Fig. 3) is similar in nature as the isotherm in the presence of NaCl at 40 °C (Fig. 2) as discussed before since in both cases $m_2^1 < m_2$. Since the plot of Γ_2^1 vs C_2 is linear for KCl, values of Δn_2 and Δn_1 obtained from eq. (11) are 0.9×10^{-3} moles of β -lactoglobulin and 4200 moles of solvent respectively per kg of casein.

The isotherm for adsorption of β lg onto casein has also been presented in Fig. 3 in the presence of KSCN. This inorganic salt is known to be protein denaturant. In the presence of KSCN, β -lactoglobulin becomes exten-

sively denatured and also this denatured protein is extensively hydrated. This will lead to the formation of denatured β lg-casein complex, which is also extensively hydrated and the excess hydration increases with increase of C_2 . Since plot of Γ_2^1 vs C_2 is linear in presence of KSCN, values of Δn_2 and Δn_1 can be estimated using eq. (11).

In Fig. 3, the isotherm for adsorption of β lg on casein have been presented at 28 °C in the presence of 6 M urea concentration. The globular protein β lg is extensively denatured in the presence of 6 M urea whereby its hydra-

Fig. 3. Plot of Γ_2^1 against C_2 in the presence of neutral salts, pH 6.5, 28 °C : (Δ) KCl, 0.05 M; (\blacksquare) KSCN, 0.05 M; (\circ) urea, 6 M.

tion is increased. The complex of β lg-casein in denatured form becomes considerably hydrated at low β lg concentration so that Γ_2^1 becomes negative. As β lg concentration is increased, the protein will be adsorbed by dehydrated casein surface to large extent in compact form leading to the formation of much less hydrated protein complex. Γ_2^1 in such situation becomes positive at a given value of C_2 . At very high β lg concentration, surface of casein will be saturated with β lg so that at a critical value Γ_2^m , Γ_2^1 attains the maximum positive value Γ_2^m (vide Table 1). At this state of saturation Δn_1 will be zero according to eq. (11).

In Fig. 1, in the presence of NaCl and Na₂SO₄ it was found that positive value of Γ_2^1 increases with the increase of C_2 due to the excess adsorption interaction of β lg with casein with simultaneous formation of protein-protein complex followed by surface dehydration of water molecules. When Γ_2^1 attains the maximum value Γ_2^m , casein appears to be free of bound water. So long Δn_1

remains positive, with increase of C_2 at higher concentration of protein²², Γ_2^1 will decrease from Γ_2^m with increase of C_2 .

In Fig. 2, Γ_2^1 values in the presence of LiCl, RbCl, CsCl and CaCl₂ are negative in low range of C_2 due to the excess hydration of protein-protein complex whereas exceeding a concentration C_2^{azeo} , the value of Γ_2^1 becomes positive due to the excess adsorption of β lg followed by surface dehydration of the protein-protein complex. In each case there is a concentration C_2^{azeo} where value of Γ_2^1 becomes zero. Such state is called azeotropic state^{22,23}. At this azeotropic state Γ_2^1 (or Γ_1^2) becomes zero so that from eqs. (11) or (12),

$$\Delta n_2 - \Delta n_1 \frac{C_2^{azeo}}{55.5} = 0$$

or,

$$\frac{\Delta n_2}{\Delta n_1} = \frac{C_2^{azeo}}{55.5} = \frac{X_2^{azeo}}{X_1} \quad (13)$$

The composition ratio of solute and solvent in the bound phase and free solution phase become same at the azeotropic state.

Affinities of β lg-casein adsorption interaction :

From all these discussions so far presented, it is found, that the globular protein β -lactoglobulin (present in milk whey) may adsorb onto the soft surface of the casein powder in aqueous media and affinity of such interaction process depends on temperature, nature and concentration of neutral salts and also concentrations of denaturants urea and KSCN.

From Table 1 it is noted that the maximum affinity expressed in terms of Γ_2^m of such adsorption interaction for 0.05 M salt concentration at 28 °C stands in the following order :

From isopiestic and other experimental investigations it has already been found that at high salt concentration range, association (or binding) of water to β lg and casein respectively are reduced due to salting out effect^{23,24}. Such reduction depends upon nature of salts following qualitatively the lyotropic or Hoffmaster series effect²⁴. In the present situation, we are studying the adsorption interaction at relatively lower salt concentrations so that the lyotropic series effect is not strictly observed.

The adsorption interaction of β lg onto the hydrophilic surface of casein depends upon the relative competition of soluble protein and water to occupy the active spots of the soft surface of casein. The maximum affinity termed as $-\Delta G^0$ is also called the maximum free energy change in kilojoules per unit surface area or unit weight of adsorbate and it is given by the expression,

$$\Delta G^0 = -RT \int_0^{a_2=1} \Gamma_2^1 d \ln a_2 \quad (12)$$

where a_2 is the activity of solute component β lg in the bulk. The value of a_2 in the bulk varies from zero to unity in the mole fraction scale. Also a_2 is equal to X_2 assuming activity coefficient equal to unity for highly dilute solution of β lg. Further with increasing value of X_2 (i.e. $C_2/55.5$), Γ_2^1 reaches the maximum value Γ_2^m at X_2 equal to X_2^m . With further increase of X_2 , X_2^m remains hypothetically constant when solution activity alters from X_2^m to unity. The value of ΔG^0 can be written using eq. (13) given by Bull²⁴ and others²³.

$$\Delta G^0 = -RT \left(\int_0^{\Gamma_2^m} \frac{\Gamma_2^1}{X_2} dX_2 - \Gamma_2^m \ln X_2 \right) \quad (13)$$

Eqs. (12) and (13) are shown to be valid for the adsorption of surfactants and proteins on fluid and solid surfaces. Negative values of ΔG^0 stands for the standard free energy change in kilojoules per unit surface area or per kg of protein when X_2 in the bulk is altered from zero to unity. Since area of hydrophilic casein surface is difficult to measure and they are expected to vary with values of Γ_2^1 , ΔG^0 is expressed in kJ per kg of casein powder for hypothetical dilution process in changing X_2 from zero to unity. The equation has been extensively used to calculate ΔG^0 for the adsorption of various proteins and DNA on different types of hydrophobic surfaces of hard and crystalline particles^{3,9,26}.

Values of ΔG^0 for the adsorption of β lg onto the surface of soft casein particles in kilojoules per kg unit have been estimated for the presence of different neutral salts using eq. (13). These are all presented in Table 1. One finds from Table 1 and also from graphical plot of ΔG^0 vs Γ_2^m (vide Fig. 4) that ΔG^0 for these salts vary linearly with Γ_2^m following eq. (14),

$$\Delta G^0 = \Delta G_B^0 \Gamma_2^m \quad (14)$$

Here ΔG_B^0 (Bull's constant)^{23,24} is expressed in kilojoules per mole of β lg adsorbed on the casein surface. It

Fig. 4. Plot of $-\Delta G^0$ against Γ_2^m .

value represents affinities between one mole of β lg with one mole of protein binding sites present on the soft casein surface. Average values of ΔG^0_B for different systems are 38 kJ per mole β lg. In the presence of different neutral salts β lg molecules adsorbed on the hydrophilic surface alters conformation due to effects of dehydration, electrostatic interaction, surface denaturation of adsorbed β lg so that Γ_2^m for different systems become different. ΔG^0 varies for these systems also following the uniform thermodynamic scale of unit activity of solute in the solution.

In Fig. 3, the isotherm for the adsorption of β lg on casein powder in the presence of 6.0 molar urea has been presented. Urea is effectively breaking water structure present on the surface of casein. Thus with increasing concentration of β lg in the bulk more and more of this globular protein is able to adsorb on the hydrophobic casein surface. The value of Γ_2^m becomes maximum on this hydrophobic surface as expected and ΔG^0 becomes maximum for this system also (vide Table 1).

Conclusion

From all these discussions, we may like to conclude that adsorbed water associated to the surface of the hy-

drophilic soft surface of casein controls the maximum affinities of β lg for the formation of the adsorption complex of β lg-casein. For dehydrated casein in presence of urea, such complex formation becomes maximum whereas practically no such complex is formed in the presence of KCl and KCNS. The standard free energies for the maximum adsorption between β lg and casein also stand in the order :

So that lyotropic series effect is only partially valid.

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References

1. H. B. Bull, *Biochem. Biophys. Adv.*, 1956, **19**, 464.
2. S. Hazra and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1992, **28**, 114.
3. S. Hazra and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1991, **28**, 287.
4. W. Norde, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1986, **23**, 267.
5. W. Norde, "Colloids and Interfaces in Life Sciences", Marcel

- Dekkar Inc., 2003, p. 285.
6. M. A. Cohen, "Stuart in Biopolymers at Interfaces", ed. M. Malmsten, Marcel Dekkar Inc., New York, 1998, p. 1.
 7. W. Norde, J. Buija and H. Lyklema, "Fundamentals of Interface and Colloid Science", Vol. 5, 'Soft Colloids', ed. J. Hyklema, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2005, p. 31.
 8. S. N. Upadhyay and D. K. Chattoraj, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1968 **26**, 140.
 9. S. A. Gani, D. C. Mukherjee and D. K. Chattoraj, *Langmuir*, 1999, **15**, 7139.
 10. S. A. Gani, D. C. Mukherjee and D. K. Chattoraj, *Langmuir*, 1999, **15**, 7130.
 11. E. Halder, K. P. Das and D. K. Chattoraj, *Biopolymers*, 2005, **77**, 286.
 12. H. A. McKenzie, "Milk Protein Chemistry and Molecular Biology", Vol. 2, Academic Press, New York, London, 1970; (a) B. K. Sadhukhan and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1983, **20**, 66.
 13. H. V. Attrnton and J. A. Newlanda, "Chemistry and Testing of Dairy Products", 4th ed., AVI Publ., Westport CT, 1979.
 14. D. F. Darling and J. Dickingson, *J. Dairy Res.*, 1979, **46**, 329.
 15. T. A. Payens, *J. Dairy Sci.*, 1956, **49**, 1317.
 16. V. A. Bloomfield and C. V. Morr, *Neth. Milk Dairy J.*, 1973, **27**, 103.
 17. C. Holt and D. S. Home, *Neth. Dairy Res.*, 1979, **46**, 329.
 18. O. H. Lowry, N. J. Roseborough, A. I. Farr and R. J. Randall, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, **193**, 265.
 19. D. K. Chattoraj, T. Imae and A. Mitra, *Langmuir*, 2004, **20**, 4903.
 20. B. K. Sadhukhan and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1983, **20**, 59.
 21. S. P. Mitra and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1978, **15**, 147.
 22. S. C. Biswas and D. K. Chattoraj, *Langmuir*, 1997, **13**, 4512.
 23. D. K. Chattoraj and K. S. Birdi, "Adsorption at Interfaces and Gibbs Surface Excess", Plenum Press, New York and London, 1984.
 24. H. B. Bull, "An Introduction to Biochemistry", 2nd ed., F. A. Davis, Philadelphia, 1971.
 25. N. Ghosh, P. Dutta, K. P. Das and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 2003, **40**, 122.
 26. S. Hajra and D. K. Chattoraj, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1994, **28**, 267.